

Factors Militating the Organization of Intramural Sport Programs in Secondary Schools: A Case Study of the Ekiti West Local Government Area of Ekiti State, Nigeria

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Abstract—The study investigated the factors militating the organization of intramural sports programs in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to identify the factors affecting the organization of sports in secondary schools and also to proffer possible solutions to these factors. The study employed the inferential statistics of chi-square (χ^2). Five research hypotheses were formulated. The population for the study was all the students in the government-owned secondary schools in Ekiti West Local Government of Ekiti State Nigeria. The sample for the study was 60 students in three schools within the local government selected through simple random sampling techniques. The instrument used for the study was a self-developed questionnaire by the researcher for data collection. The instrument was presented to experts and academicians in the field of Human Kinetics and Health Education for construct and content validation. A reliability test was conducted which involves 10 students who are not part of the study. The test-retest coefficient of 0.74 was obtained which attested to the fact that the instrument was reliable enough for the study. The validated questionnaire was administered to the students in their various schools by the researcher with the help of two research assistants; the questionnaires were filled and returned to the researcher immediately. The data collected were analyzed using the descriptive statistics of frequency count, percentage and mean to analyze demographic data in section A of the questionnaire, while inferential statistics of chi-square was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The results of the study revealed that personnel, fund, schedule (time) were significant factors that affect the organization of intramural sport programs among students in secondary schools in Ekiti West Local Government Area of the State. The study also revealed that organization of intramural sports programs among students of secondary schools will improve and motivate students' participation in sports beyond the local level. However, facilities and equipment is not a significant factor affecting the organization of intramural sports among secondary school students in Ekiti West Local Government Area.

Keywords—Challenge, militating, intramural sport, programs.

I. INTRODUCTION

SPORTS today are a global phenomenon, and at the same time, very dynamic, this is because sports are changing with time and technological development. Most of the

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countries all over the world today spend a reasonable part of their annual budgets on youth development programs with the aim of maximizing the potentials of tomorrow's leaders. According to scientific evidence from history archeology and sociology, sport has been an essential element in all cultures world-wide and throughout the evolution of the human race. The word sport was derived from "disport" meaning to "divert itself" carrying the original implication of people diverting their activities [1]. Sport, according to [2], was defined as a unifying instrument that brings together humans irrespective of race, gender, class and other parameters. He further stated that sport has emerged as a global cultural institution that brings or unites the world together and has become part of human nature and transcends man-made bias and other hindrances placed before humans. The word "intramural" is derived from the Latin word "intra" which means "within" and "mural" meaning walls. Intramural sports program are recreational sports organized within school, college and university settings which involves club teams that compete regularly. These organized recreational sports programs were used to promote the wellness of students, give students a chance to socially interact with their peers and also enable them to begin to define their independence and find themselves during this period, because school life involves more than just academic achievement. The most important aspect of the intramural program lies in its educational objectives. Some of the objectives are primarily social and are designed for wholesome fun, to develop teamwork, loyalty, reward and achievement, friendship and good fellowship, while other objectives are primarily physical and psychological such as improvement of health, personality development, ability to meet effectively the mental and emotional stresses and acquisition of lifelong leisure-time skills. There is therefore substantial interest in how teenagers are spending their leisure time inside and outside the school day, and the types of activities which are important to their development. Studies have been carried out that support either being involved, being over-involved, or not being involved at all in intramural and extracurricular activities and how participation can challenge what becomes of youth in the future based on participation in activities inside and outside the school day. Intramural sports have been a vehicle used in bringing activities to the door step of all. It coordinates all sporting activities at the grass root level so that hidden talents

in sport are discovered and given equal opportunity to participate [3]. Different levels of activity involvement and participation may positively impact the level of participation and challenge the individuals' development [4]. Well organized and structured sport activities fosters a healthy state of mind and body due to the support and opportunities that are present in it unlike the unstructured and substandard after school options for adolescents. Students that participated in well structured sporting activities are more likely to have respect for variety, play according to the rules and as well contribute as one of the team members whether in sports, scouting or clubs. Therefore, the researcher aims at investigating the challenges/factors militating the organizing of intramural sports programs in secondary schools in Ekiti West Local Government Area of Ekiti State. Ekiti state government is expected to implement both intramural and extramural sports programs (activities) in all school levels (preparatory, primary, secondary and tertiary) in order for them to achieve the Millennium Development Goal and to enforce the UNESCO charter for Physical Education and Sport [5]. In view of this importance, the government has a great responsibility to enforce the implementation of intramural and extramural sports programs in schools for the promotion of health and attainment of education across all levels. It was discovered that intramural sports in secondary schools are often conducted or organized in view of the fact that there are many problems such as inadequate facilities, inadequate equipment and some school administrators tending to show apathy in sports programs in their school, this story is the same in schools in Ekiti West. This study therefore wanted to find out the factors militating against the organization of intramural sports programs among secondary school students in Ekiti West Local Government Area of Ekiti State.

II. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

- H_01 : Physical education personnel will not significantly affect the organization of intramural sports programs in secondary schools in Ekiti West Local Government.
- H_02 : Fund will not significantly affect the organization of intramural sports programs in secondary schools in Ekiti West Local Government.
- H_03 : Facilities and equipment will not significantly affect the organization of intramural sports programs in secondary schools in Ekiti West Local Government.
- H_04 : Schedule or time will not significantly affect the organization of intramural sports programs in secondary schools in Ekiti West Local Government.
- H_05 : Intramural sport will not improve sport enthusiasm and participation among secondary school students in Ekiti West Local Government.

A. Research Methodology

In order to obtain a good and relevant data for this study, different methods were used. The following section describes the design of the study, research setting, population of the study, sample and sampling techniques, research instruments,

validity and reliability of instrument, method of data collection and method of data analysis.

B. Design of the Study

This study employs a descriptive survey method because the intention of the study is to assess the existing situation and to describe opinions that are the factors militating intramural sports programs in respect to practices and organization. With regard to the use of descriptive survey research method, [6] have argued that this method is concerned with conditions that are in existence, opinions that are held, process that are going on, effects that are evident or trends that are developing. Therefore, the method is preferred on the ground that factors of intramural sport programs are better perceived from the opinion survey of the students in the schools. Also, the inferential statistics of Chi-square was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level.

III. SOURCES OF DATA

Data were collected from two sources: primary and secondary. The primary sources of the study were key respondents from the schools which are students of secondary schools in Ekiti West Local Government of Ekiti State. In addition, information was also collected from secondary sources for the study which are data collected from reference books mainly from published research materials and unpublished materials, internet and deferent sources.

A. Research Population

Three secondary schools which are located in Ekiti West were purposively selected for this study. The main reason for selecting this site was because the researcher has previous knowledge and information on the sample schools with the hopes that he can get sufficient information for his study and there was no significant research work done in these schools in Ekiti West, particularly in this area of study.

IV. SAMPLING POPULATION AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

The entire secondary schools in Ekiti West Local Government in Ekiti State were considered as the study area. This area is decided to be taken as a setting for this study because the researcher has previous knowledge and information on the sample schools. Out of the existing 20 secondary schools in Ekiti West Local Government, three schools were purposively selected and used as data sources. The remaining schools are deliberately excluded because they have very few numbers of students who are schooling there. These sampled schools both have factors which are discouraging and encouraging regarding the organization of intramural sports programs. Accordingly, the selected secondary schools include:

- i. Okemesi Grammar School, Okemesi Ekiti,
- ii. Aramoko Grammar School, Aramoko Ekiti,
- iii. Erinjiyan Grammar School, Erinjiyan Ekiti.

After selection of the sample schools, the selection of the respondents of the study was conducted through simple random sampling technique. Accordingly, data were collected

from 20 students from each school making a total of 60 respondents all together from the three schools.

A. Data Collection Instrument

The research instrument for the study consist a self-developed questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of two sections. Section A of the questionnaire consists of the demographic data of the respondents while the section B aspect contains items to test the variables under study. The questionnaire is made up of a 4-point modified Likert scale of strongly agreed (SA), agreed (A), disagreed (D), strongly disagreed (SA). The questionnaire was given to experts in the field of physical education for construct and content validation, while a fresh reliability test was conducted which involves 10 students of Edu High School, Erio Ekiti in the same local government who are not part of the study. The result obtained attested that the instrument was reliable enough for the study.

B. Data Collection Procedure

The researcher together with his research assistants went to the schools with a letter of introduction to the school principals to seek their consent and to brief them about the study. On getting the approval from the principals, the questionnaires was personally distributed to the students in the classrooms, it was filled and returned to the researcher immediately. This made it possible to retrieve the total number of questionnaires administered.

V. METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The researcher used descriptive statistics of frequency count, mean and percentage to analyze the demographic data in section A of the questionnaire, while inferential statistics of Chi-square (χ^2) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level.

VI. ANALYSIS PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION

Result of the analyzes on the demographic data shows that 20 (33.3%) of the respondents were male and 40 (66.7%) were female, which implies that more female students participated in the study than male students, the religious analyzes shows that 48 (80%) of the respondents were Christians, 12 (20%) were Muslims and other religions 0 (0%), which means more Christians participated in the study than Muslims. It was also observed from the study that respondents to the questionnaires was made up of 18 (30%) students from the senior secondary school class 1 (SS1), 13 (21.7%) students from the senior secondary school class 2 (SS2) and 29 (48.3%) students from the senior secondary school class 3 (SS3), which implies that majority of the respondents were in senior secondary school class 3 (SS3).

From the analysis, the hypothesis which states that physical education personnel will not significantly affect the organization of intramural sports programs in the selected schools has a calculated (χ^2) value of 71.859 with degree of freedom of 9, which is greater than the table value of 16.92 at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was therefore

rejected, which means that physical education personnel will significantly affect the organization of intramural sports programs in selected schools in Ekiti West metropolis.

TABLE I
 BIO-DATA OF RESPONDENTS IN PERCENTAGES

Variable	No. of Respondent	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	20	33.3
Female	40	66.7
Total	60	100
Religion		
Christianity	48	80
Islam	12	20
Others	0	0
Total	60	100
Class		
SS 1	18	30.0
SS 2	13	21.7
SS 3	29	48.3
Total	60	100

TABLE II
 X2 RESULT OF THE RESPONDENTS ON FACTORS MILITATING THE ORGANIZATION OF INTRAMURAL SPORT PROGRAMS N=60

Variable	Cal. X 2	Df	Critical value	Decision
H ₀₁	71.859	9	16.92	Rejected
H ₀₂	90.559	9	16.92	Rejected
H ₀₃	13.982	9	16.92	Accepted
H ₀₄	36.914	9	16.92	Rejected
H ₀₅	75.558	6	12.59	Rejected

p<0.05

The second hypothesis which states that funds will not significantly affect the organization of intramural sports programs in the selected secondary schools has a calculated (χ^2) value of 90.559 with degree of freedom of 9, which is greater than the table value of 16.92 at 0.05 level of significance was rejected and confirms that funds will significantly affect the organization of intramural sports programs in selected schools in Ekiti West metropolis.

The third hypothesis states that facilities and equipment will not significantly affect the organization of intramural sports programs in selected schools has a calculated (χ^2) value of 13.982 with a degree of freedom of 9, which is lesser than the table value of 16.92 at 0.05 level of significance was accepted which means that facilities and equipment will not truly significantly affect the organization of intramural sports programs in the selected schools in Ekiti West metropolis, that is the assumption is correct.

The fourth hypothesis which states that schedule/time will not significantly affect the organization of intramural sports programs in the selected secondary schools has a calculated (χ^2) value of 36.914 with degree of freedom of 9, which is greater than the table value of 16.92 at 0.05 level of significance was rejected and confirms that schedule/time will significantly affect the organization of intramural sports programs in selected schools in Ekiti West metropolis.

The fifth hypothesis, which is the last, states that organization of intramural sports will not improve sport enthusiasm and participation among students in the selected secondary schools has a calculated (χ^2) value of 75.558 with

degree of freedom of 6, which is greater than the table value of 12.59 at 0.05 level of significance was rejected and confirms that organization of intramural sports programs among students will improve their enthusiasm and participation in sports in selected schools in Ekiti West metropolis.

VII. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the study, it was concluded that lack of physical education personnel affects the organization of intramural sports programs, and this was supported by [7] who explained that the teaching of physical education should be a task undertaken by competent personnel. The effectiveness and efficiency of organized intramural sport should be determined by the level of competency of teachers who are in the field of physical education. It was also discovered that funding is another factor that will affect the organization of intramural sports programs, and this was in line with [8] who said that intramural sport organizer should be given adequate finance for administering the program. Funding should be made available for the schools to procure the necessary facilities and equipment and also to buy materials or awards to be given to students which may serve as a motivator to the students. Another factor affecting the organization of intramural sports programs is schedule or time and it was also discovered that organization of intramural sports programs improves the students' enthusiasm and participation in sports.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The following conclusion was drawn based on the result of the finding:

Shortage of funding impacted the organization of intramural sports programs; Shortage of qualified personnel in PE negatively affected the intramural sports program, poor timing or wrong scheduling of sporting activities affected intramural sports programs, and the organization of intramural sports programs in schools will improve and motivate students' participation in sports.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

To enhance sound and effective organization and administration of intramural sports programs in secondary schools in Ekiti West Local Government, the following have been recommended:

- There should be adequate employment of qualified personnel to handle intramural sports programs in secondary schools or even at all educational levels. This can be done through employment of trained persons, athletes and students with good skills can be trained on the basic skills, rules and regulations guiding such sports and constant training of these persons can offset the inadequacy of personnel.
- Ministries of education at the federal, state and local levels should support schools financially to organize sporting programs.
- Concerned bodies such as parents, stakeholders, and good hearted Nigerians, sport lovers etc should assist in

training personnel as well as help organize sports since the concerned body will also benefit from the process.

- Conferences, training, workshop, symposium, meeting and consultation should be organized regularly.
- Preparatory schools sport program should be encouraged and organized regularly.

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